

USLUBIYAT HAQIDA UMUMIY TUSHUNCHA

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada nutq uslublari va adabiy tilning ijtimoiy hayotning ma'lum sohasi doirasida qo'llanilishi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: uslubiyat, so'zlashuv uslubi, badiiy uslub, rasmiy uslub, ilmiy uslub, publitsistik uslub.

Hammaga ma'lumki, odamlar turli nutqiy vaziyatlarda turlicha gapiradi. Bunda nutq tuzishdan bir maqsad bo'ladi. Shu maqsad asosida, ijtimoiy hayotdagi ma'lum bir soha doirasida (masalan, ilmiy, rasmiy, badiiy kabilar) muayyan nutqiy vaziyatda qo'llaniladigan til shakli nutq shakli hisoblanadi. Har bir uslub o'ziga xos til xususiyatlariga ega bo'ladi. Bu xususiyatlarni bilish, to'g'ri gapirish va yozish, aniq, ta'sirli va tugal nutq tuzish imkoniyatini beradi. Nutq uslublariga tegishli til xususiyatlarining jami uslubiyat deyiladi. O'zbek tilshunosligining ma'lum darajada yangi sohasi hisoblanadigan, nutq uslublarini o'rganuvchi bo'limi uslubiyat yoki uslubshunoslik deb ataladi. So'zlar ham ma'lum nutq uslubiga xoslanish-xoslanmaslik darajasiga ko'ra uslubiy xoslangan va uslubiy betaraf so'zlarga bo'linadi.

Ayrim nutq uslubi doirasidagina qo'llaniladigan so'zlar uslubiy xoslangan so'zlar, bunday xususiyatga ega bo'lmagan so'zlar uslubiy betaraf so'zlar hisoblanadi.

Uslubiy betaraf so'zlar: maktab, shaxmat, ovqat, futbol, eshik, kitob, ota, piyola, dars.

Uslubiy xoslangan so'zlar: maqola, binobarin, dudoq, meng, istiora, muhtaram, nota, shartnoma kabilar.

O'zbek tilining quyidagi nutq uslublari mavjud: 1) so'zlashuv uslubi; 2) badiiy uslub; 3) ilmiy uslub; 4) rasmiy uslub; 5) publitsistik uslub

Bulardan so'zlashuv uslubigina og'zaki, qolganlari esa yozma va og'zaki hisoblanadi.

Ilmiy asar, ilmiy ma'ruza matni yozma nutqqa, ilmiy ma'ruzaning o'zi esa og'zaki nutqqa xos. Badiiy uslubning ham yozma va og'zaki (xalq og'zaki ijodi) ko'rinishi mavjud.

So‘zlashiv uslubi. Kundalik hayotda, ko‘cha-ko‘yda, maktabda, jamoat joylarida kishilarning fikr almashish jarayonida qo‘llaniladigan nutq uslubi. Bu uslub adabiy va oddiy so‘zlashuv uslublariga bo‘linadi. Ma‘lum adabiy til me‘yorlariga qat‘iy amal qilingan, tartibga solingan uslub adabiy so‘zlashuv uslubi, adabiy til me‘yorlariga har doim ham amal qilinavermaydigan erkin muloqot shakli oddiy so‘zlashuv uslubidir. So‘zlovchi bu uslubda nutqiy vositalarni tejashga, ya‘ni qisqartirishga harakat qiladi. So‘zlashuv nutqidagi sodda gaplar ko‘pincha fe‘l bilan ifodalangan kesimning yo‘qligi bilan xarakterlanadi.

– Dars ikkinchidan (bizning darslarimiz ikkinchi sentabrdan boshlanadi).

Ba‘zan so‘zlashuv uslubida shevaga xos so‘zlar, qo‘pol so‘zlar kuzatiladi, bu so‘zlovchining madaniy nutqda oqsoqlanishidan darak beradi.

Badiiy uslub: Ma‘lum bir voqelikni badiiy tasvir vositalari orqali ifodalovchi, shu yo‘l bilan tinglovchiga estetik ta‘sir etuvchi uslub. Badiiy uslubning o‘ziga xosligi shuki, unda adabiy tilning barcha imkoniyatlarini o‘z ichiga olishi, o‘zbek shevalari, kasb-hunarga doir leksik birliklar, bugungi kunga kelib iste‘moldan chiqqan tarixiy so‘zlar qahramonlar nutqi orqali namoyon bo‘ladi.

Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiyning “Padarkush” dramasi dan parcha

Domla: – Shariat ilmi va zaruriyati diniya bilmoq uchun boyvachchani o‘qutmak, albatta, sizga lozimdur.

Boy: – Shariat ilmini o‘qutmakni lozim bilmayman, chunku ani mufti yo imom va muazzin qilmoqchi emasman. Azbaski, davlatim anga yetar.

Ilmiy uslub: Til birliklarining fan doirasida, ilmiy bayon jarayonida ishlatilishi bu uslubning shakllanishiga asos bo‘ladi. Ilmiy uslubda ham fikr aniq bo‘lishi kerak. Ilmiy uslubning janr xususiyatlari ham mavjud. Monografiya, risola, darslik, o‘quv qo‘llanmasi, ma‘ruza matni, referat kabilar shu janr ko‘rinishlari. Daliliy ma‘lumotlar asosida chiqarilgan ilmiy xulosalarga asoslangan fikrni aniq izchil shaklda bayon qiluvchi uslub ilmiy uslub deyiladi. Ilmiy uslub ikki guruhga bo‘linadi. 1) sof ilmiy uslub 2) ilmiy-ommabop uslub.

Ilmiy uslubga misol:

Timsohlar sudralib yuruvchilarning eng qadimiy guruhlaridan hisoblanadi. Ular 300 ming yil ilgari paydo bo'lgan. Hozir yashab turgan timsohlar turkumi turli-tuman arxozavrlar kenja sinfining qoldig'i sanaladi.

Publitsistik uslub: Publitsistika davrning muhim, dolzarb masalalarini o'quvchi yoshlarga, tinglovchilarga gazeta-jurnal, radio, televideniya orqali yetkazish uchun xizmat qiladi. Bu uslub ham yozma, ham og'zaki shaklda bo'ladi. Televideniya chiqayotgan siyosiy xabar, yangiliklar og'zaki shakliga, ijtimoiy-siyosiy masalalarga bag'ishlangan maqola, felyeton, murojaatnomalar yozma shakliga kiradi. Publitsistik uslub, tashviqot va targ'ibot uslubi bo'lganligi uchun unda siyosiy faollik, o'tkir notiqlik, mantiqiy mulohaza kabi belgilar ustunlik qiladi. Publitsistik nutqda ta'sirchan so'z birikmalardan, maqol va hikmatli so'zlardan ham foydalaniladi.

Publitsistik uslubga misol:

Hayot – ajoyib o'qituvchi: insho yozdiradi, o'zingga tekshirtiradi, bahoni esa boshqalar qo'yadi. U hech kimga yo unvon yo guvohnoma bermaydi. (Omon Matjon)

Rasmiy uslub. Bu uslub o'zbek tilining davlat ishlari, huquqiy masalalar hamda diplomatik munosabatlarda namoyon bo'ladi. Adabiy tilning yozma rasmiy shakliga xos, muayyan nutqiy qolip, qat'iy odat tusiga kirib qolgan shakllariga ega nutq uslubi rasmiy uslub sanaladi. Bunda aniqlik asosiy rol o'ynaydi. Jargonlar, oddiy so'zlashuv uslubida ishlatiladigan so'zlar, emotsional-ekspressiv bo'yoqqa ega so'zlarning ishlatilishi me'yor sanalmaydi va bu jihati bilan boshqa uslublardan farq qiladi. Har bir hujjatning o'ziga xos bayon etish qolipi mavjud. Rasmiy uslub deyarli yozma shaklda bo'ladi. Rasmiy hujjatlar qisqa, aniq va hammaga tushunarli tarzda namoyon bo'ladi. Bu uslubda darak, buyruq gaplardan foydalaniladi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling "Between Two Doors", the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz "yomon xastalik", "og'ir dard", "yomon kasallik" kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

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